

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17180407

Effect of Perceived Job Support and Job Satisfaction on Workers Productivity; A survey of Non academic staff of Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto

Abdullahi Abubakar & Abubakar Isah Baba

Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study examines Perceived Job Support and Job Satisfaction on Workers Productivity in Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto. The questionnaire was adopted as the research instrument to elicit the needed data from 377 respondents. The data analysis employed Smart PLS SEM 3.2.8, a second-generation statistical methodology developed to address the drawbacks of first-generation statistical methods including Manova, Factor analysis, and Analysis of Variance. The results indicate that there is a significant relationship between Perceived Job Support and Job Satisfaction; Based on the findings, the study recommends that reward framework of both academic and nonacademic members of Polytechnic. This would enhance Job Satisfaction, innovativeness and the craving to acquire new knowledge among workers.

Keywords: Job Support, Job Satisfaction, Workers Productivity

INTRODUCTION

Achieving high-level performance through productivity and efficiency has consistently been a top priority for organizations. To accomplish this, it is essential to have a highly satisfied workforce that feels supported by the organization, as this is crucial for enhancing overall performance. When workers are satisfied, they tend to put in more effort and perform their jobs more effectively. Consequently, organizations strive to cultivate a satisfied workforce to ensure the organization's well-being. Nevertheless, the overall performance of the organization relies on the efficient and effective performance of each individual employee. As a result, every organization significantly depends on the performance of its individual employees to achieve high productivity. The effort an employee puts in is a key factor in determining their performance. When employees feel satisfied with their jobs, they are more likely to be motivated to exert increased effort in their performance. This, in turn, contributes to the overall performance of the organization. In summary, the satisfaction of individual employees, along with their effort and commitment, is vital for the organization's success.

Perceived job support refers to the efforts made by organizations to assist their employees in applying the skills, knowledge, and attitudes acquired from training programs (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). As stated by Bhatti et al. (2013), organizations have a significant impact on the effectiveness of training. Without organizational support, the transfer of training process is unlikely to succeed. This is due to the tendency of employees to lose focus when they are not monitored or supervised. It is recognized as one of the most effective methods for enhancing training transfer, a notion supported by various studies (Baldwin & Ford, 1988; Ismail et al., 2010).

Job satisfaction, conversely, is a complex and multifaceted concept that can hold different meanings for various individuals. It is primarily an attitude or an internal state. This feeling can be linked to a sense of achievement, whether it is measurable or subjective (Mullins, 1999). He explores job satisfaction by assessing the alignment between the organization's expectations and the employee's aspirations, as well as the correspondence between what employees desire and what they actually

receive. He highlighted that the degree of job satisfaction is influenced by a broad range of factors related to

- Individual (i.e. personality, education, intelligence and abilities, age, marital status and orientation to work);
- Social factors (i.e. relationship with co-workers, group working and norms and opportunity for interaction);
- Cultural factors (i.e. attitudes, beliefs and values);
- Organizational factors (i.e. nature and size, formal structure, personnel policies and procedures, employee relations, nature of the work, supervision and styles of leadership, management systems and working conditions); and
- Environmental factors (i.e. economic, social, technical and governmental influences).

According to Sweeny and Mcfarln (2002), job satisfaction is the outcome of a psychological comparison process of how well different components of an employment (such as pay, autonomy, and workload) match their desired level of satisfaction. Employees are therefore less satisfied with their work when there is a greater disparity between what they have and what they desire from them; employees are generally most content with their jobs when their desires and what they have align. The sum of an employee's comparisons between what the job offers and what they want in different areas is their overall job happiness. The notion that employees' feelings are greatly influenced by perceived importance has managerial ramifications as well. Obisi (2003) identified several factors that influence job satisfaction, including fair pay, favorable working conditions, effective management, job stability, chances for advancement, a positive and supportive atmosphere, amicable relationships with coworkers, and a respectful interaction between superiors and subordinates. Consequently, we can deduce that job satisfaction represents an individual's assessment of their job and work environment. This research intends to examine the Effect of Perceived Job Support and Job Satisfaction on Workers Productivity, with particular reference to Non academic staff of Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto.

Statement of the Problem

The shifting landscape of competition in various industries in Nigeria is reflected in the growing presence of foreign investors and a multitude of multinational corporations, along with local stakeholders (independent marketers), which necessitates a robust organizational structure to help these firms keep their top talent. According to Gunter and Furnham (1996), job satisfaction can directly lead to beneficial work outcomes. Positive work incentives are those that enhance the work experience, such as an appealing work environment, effective personnel policies, a range of benefits, a well-defined job structure, and competitive compensation. A supportive work environment fosters motivation, establishes effective personnel policies, creates a conducive atmosphere, and ensures the availability of benefits, leading to job satisfaction and fair compensation. However, negative work incentives include those incentives that make work boring, unchallenging and dissatisfying. They lead to increased absenteeism, turnover and accidents. Thus to prevent these negative work outcomes, there is a need to find out which factors within the organizational context can lead to satisfaction among non academic staff of UAS polytechnic so as to continually have productive, satisfied and contented employees. Nevertheless, it is essential to emphasize that the researcher recognizes that elements such as effective communication, a proper reward system, and opportunities for advancement can either promote or hinder both favorable and unfavorable work results, which, if not sufficiently established, may lead to employee turnover. Such comparative studies would provide the researcher the chance to discern differences in employee job satisfaction and their influence on employee performance

Several elements have been recognized in research as influencing the degree to which dissatisfaction is linked to employee performance and compensation. The influence of these factors differed and are closely linked to beliefs, management of factors, and levels of tolerance (Delery and Doty, 2006; Doty, Glick and Huber, 2003). Factors that can improve or hinder academic work performance include the emphasis on administrative style by top management, workload, performance feedback, and support from superiors

Additionally, job satisfaction is significant to the physical and mental health of employees, meaning that job satisfaction is important for human well-being (Oshagbemi, 1999). Grasping the elements that contribute to job satisfaction is important for enhancing the well-being of many individuals. Although striving for enhanced satisfaction holds humanitarian significance, Smith, Kendall, and Hulin (1969) noted that, while it may appear "trite," satisfaction is a valid objective on its own. Thus, aside from its humanitarian value, it seems financially sensible to explore ways to enhance job satisfaction. Thus, it is essential to recognize variables in the organizational context that can enhance the job satisfaction of employees within an organization. Many prior studies have tried to clarify a worker's job satisfaction as determined by the personal traits of the individual and the attributes of the job itself. Additional elements that seem to influence the efficient operation of organizations encompass management and leadership approaches, ambiguous rules and regulations within personnel policies, excessive workload, ineffective communication with supervisors along with vague communication channels, feelings of boredom and frustration stemming from insufficient support from superiors, lack of a suitable career progression, unchallenging tasks, and inadequate benefits as anticipated in the working environment (Marriner-Tomey, 1999)

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the effect of perceive job support and job satisfaction on employee performance of the Non academic staff of UAS polytechnic Sokoto Nigeria. The specific objectives are therefore listed below;

1. To find out the relationship that exists between perceive job support and Productivity of Non academic staff of UAS polytechnic Sokoto
2. To determines the relationship job satisfaction and productivity of Non academic staff of UAS polytechnic Sokoto

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between perceive job support and Productivity of Non academic staff of UAS polytechnic Sokoto?
2. What is the relationship between job satisfaction and productivity of Non academic staff of UAS polytechnic Sokoto?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee: An individual who works part-time or full-time under a contract of employment, whether oral or written, express or implied, and has recognized rights and duties also called worker.

Satisfaction: refer to discharge, extinguishment, or retirement of an obligation to the acceptance of the obligor, or fulfillment of a claim.

Productivity: the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. In a contract, performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract

Perceive Job Support

Perceive Job Support refers, organizational initiatives to assist staff in exhibiting the abilities, know-how, and dispositions acquired during the training program are referred to as support (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Bhatti et al. (2013) assert that organizations have a significant impact on the efficacy of training. The training process cannot be successfully transferred without the organization's assistance. This is because when an employee is not being watched over or supervised, they have a tendency to lose attention. Numerous studies have backed it up as one of the most effective techniques for improving training transfer (Baldwin & Ford, 1988; Ismail et al., 2010).

Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction is defined as a perspective that people hold regarding their job. That is the degree to which individuals perceive positive or negative feelings regarding the inherent elements and/or external factors of their job. King and Williamson (2005) asserted that job satisfaction is the disparity between expectations suggested by an individual whose role involves contributions related to their expectations based on the opinions expressed, it can be inferred that job satisfaction reflects an individual's reaction to what. They anticipate what they will receive after completing the task. Where it pertains to the work conditions, teamwork among staff, advantages and additional elements. If there's a slight discrepancy between expectations and outcomes will lead that individual to feel content as indeed the opposite a perspective that people hold regarding their jobs. That is the degree

to which individuals have positive or negative feelings regarding the inherent elements and/or external factors of their job. King and Williamson (2005) mentioned that job satisfaction is the disparity between expectations suggested by a person whose role is to contribute regarding their expectations (Millán, Hessels, Thurik, and Aguado, 2013)

Perceive Job Support and Workers Productivity

Organizational support theory suggests that PJS indicates how much employees feel that their organization appreciates their efforts and is concerned about their welfare. POS might create a perceived duty to be concerned for the organization's well-being and to assist it in reaching its objectives. In the meantime, PJS ought to address socio emotional needs by integrating organizational membership and role status into their social identity, while enhancing employees' perceptions that greater performance leads to organizational rewards. Employers desire workers to be committed and faithful to their jobs. When employers offer significant support to their employees, following the principle of reciprocity, employees are inclined to emotionally engage with their organizations, resulting in a low chance of turnover and high job performance

Rhoades et al. showed in a meta-analysis of 70 studies that employees' PJS might enhance JP. Nonetheless, a few earlier studies have shown conflicting outcomes. Stamper et al. found that POS had no connection to task performance in sales personnel. Additionally, past research has indicated that PJS affects various organizational experience factors and might not have a direct impact on job performance. Consequently, it remains unclear if PJS is directly linked to JP or if other factors mediate this relationship for university faculty members. In our research, we examine the connections between antecedents (two aspects of organizational justice and demographic traits) and PJS, as well as between PJS and EP. Based on the above, this paper hypothesizes that

H1: There is a significant relationship between Perceive Job Support and Workers Productivity

Job Satisfaction and Workers Productivity

A thorough evaluation has been conducted regarding the connection between job satisfaction and performance in numerous organizations. The outcomes of these studies were varied. Cummings (1970) identified three key aspects of the connection between job satisfaction and performance: satisfaction leads to performance, performance leads to satisfaction, and rewards influence both performance and satisfaction. Numerous researchers discovered these three perspectives in their findings. Mirvis and Lawler (1977) carried out a study, and the results indicated a connection between job satisfaction and performance.

Berghe and Hyung (2011) carried out research on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance, with a total of 119 respondents who were employed by company X, an international firm in the service sector. Company X's biggest offices included Finland, which had 58 respondents selected, while 25 were from Sweden, and 12 were chosen from the Denmark office for this study. In this study, the Atmosphere Questionnaire was utilized, encompassing six different categories. The findings of this study indicated a weak relationship between job satisfaction and performance, and there was no causal link established

Hussin (2011) also examined the connection between job satisfaction and performance in Klang Valley across various companies within the Trade Winds Group, with 115 respondents selected for this research. This study utilized five dimensions to assess job satisfaction, specifically pay, promotion, the work itself, supervision, and co-workers. This study found that job satisfaction and job performance are linked through four distinct dimensions of job satisfaction: promotion, the nature of the work, supervision, and colleagues, while compensation was not part of this finding. It is important to recognize that position and job performance are distinct from one another. Finally, the findings of this research showed that a 17.8% improvement happened due to job satisfaction and its aspects such as salary, advancement, the nature of the work, management, and colleagues in job performance. Based on the above, this study hypothesizes that

H1: There is a significant relationship between Job Satisfaction and Workers Productivity

Underpinning theory

Multiple theories, including organization and administrative theory, progressive utilization theory (PROUT), ability motivation opportunity theory, and resource-based view, explain how companies can leverage internal resources to gain competitive advantages (RBV). The emphasis of organizational and administrative theory lies in the rationale behind organizational actions. While the PROUT emphasizes enhancing financial independence, RBV highlights the ability to leverage an

organization's resources for a competitive edge, and cooperatives instinctively adjust. AMO further highlights several additional facets of how HRM illustrates the link between performance and outcomes (Paauwe, 2009).

Nevertheless, a significant weakness in organizational and administrative theory is its focus on structure instead of resources (Acedo, Barroso, & Galan, 2006). Maheshvarananda and Branch (2010) only validated the practical importance and relevance of the PROUT theory, while AMO equally focuses on individual-level factors rather than organizational ones, including abilities (A), which encompasses employees' knowledge, skills, and competencies; motivation (M), which assesses how well employees' skills align with tasks; and opportunity (O), representing the chances available to employees and the means of providing those opportunities (Boselie, Dietz, & Boon, 2005). RBV possesses an advantage over PROUT, AMO, organizational and administrative theories because it can effectively assemble resources and capabilities of the organization to attain sustained competitive advantage, which in turn enhances OP. RBV on its own can clearly elucidate the connections between the variables, including mediating relationships. Based on this argument, RBV is considered as underpinning theory on this present study.

Resource Based View (RBV)

The resource-based view (RBV) of the firm can be traced to its creators, Barney and Penrose, over 25 years ago. Wernerfelt (1984) provided evidence that the RBV viewpoint of a company could enhance the logical justification for the theory. Penrose (1959) is considered one of the initial researchers to acknowledge the effect of organizational resources on their competitive standing. According to Barney (1991), this research emphasizes the additional value that individuals can contribute to an organization, as articulated in the resource-based view (RBV) of that organization. Barney's theory, which considers human capital as delicate, gained increased significance for this effort. Individuals are regarded as assets, and companies will benefit from investing in them. The concept of competitive advantage was initially introduced by Ansoff in 1992, who stated that it stems from an organization's ability to provide a significant contribution. By the turn of the 20th century, management had perfected the understanding that individuals—not any other resources—were what distinguished an organization and that all other resources relied on them to generate value (Khavul, Bruton, & Wood, 2009).

Based on the RBV, it can be deduced that internal resources (such as promotion opportunities) can strengthen established competitive advantage by encouraging the development of firm-specific unique opportunities (Lado & Wilson, 1994). Again, the ongoing unparalleled performance and the edge that numerous companies hold in their distinctive ability to handle HRM processes (Caliskan, 2010). Offstein, Gnyawali, and Cobb (2005) state that the RBV posits an organization's competitive edge stems from its unique skill sets, advantageous resources of valuable information, and effectiveness in decision-making. The RBV was initially meant to shift from a product perspective focused on organizations to a resource perspective, enhancing the understanding of strategic management. Manroop et al. (2014) argue that, from an RBV standpoint, ethical conduct is linked to enhancing value for promotion chances and OP by playing a significant role in attaining organizational performance. It emphasizes how ethical behavior is perceived to offer strategic value for companies and how human resource systems could influence that value. Recent research based on the company's RBV has sought to illustrate both theoretically and empirically how organizational assets can generate strategic value for an organization (Barney, 1991; Barney, 1986 value building resources includes; culture (Barney, 1986), learning (Fiol & Lyles, 1985), procedures (Nelson & Winter, 1982),

Research Framework

The research framework will be framed to examine the role of Perceived Job Support and Job Satisfaction on Workers Productivity

Research Framework

METHODOLOGY

This research utilized a cross-sectional design, with data gathered through self-administered surveys. The unit of analysis consisted of nonacademic personnel from the Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto, State Nigeria. Three hundred seventy-seven key informants were requested to complete the survey package for their organizations. The chosen sample consists of 377 individuals from a total population of 2200, following the guidelines of Sekeran and Bougie (2013) and the sample size table by Salkind. Smart PLS SEM 3.2.8 was employed for data analysis; it is a second-generation analytical method designed to address the limitations of first-generation statistical techniques such as MANOVA, factor analysis, and ANOVA. It was also deemed crucial in assessing measured, latent variables and intricate models (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014, 2016). A content validity assessment was also performed to ascertain the consistency of the study instrument. All the instruments employed in the questionnaire were modified from multiple sources, with appropriate internal consistency reliability and validity verified in the literature. The target population of this study comprised employees at Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic. During the field survey, 377 questionnaires were issued to gather information from participants. The information on Perceived Job Support, Job Satisfaction, and Worker Productivity was gathered using a random sampling method. Nonetheless, from the 377 questionnaires distributed, the researcher only received 228 back. Details on demographic features of the respondents are shown in Table 1

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

S/N	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage
1	Age	20-39 years old.	141	61.8
		40-59 years old.	62	27.2
		60 years and above	25	10.9
2	Marital Status	Married	198	86.8
		Single	30	13.1
3	Work Experience	1-10 years	98	42.9
		11-20 years	105	46
		20 years and above	25	10.9
4	Qualification	SSCE certificate	62	27.1
		Diploma	111	48.6
		Degree	43	18.8

Table 1 indicates that approximately 61.8 percent of the study population falls within the 20-39-year age group, while 27.2 percent are in the 40-59 age category. Approximately 10.9 percent of the participants were aged 60 or older. The table shows that 86.8 percent of those surveyed are married, whereas 13.1 percent remain single. The table also revealed that 42.9 percent of the participants

possess 1-10 years of work experience, 46 percent have 11-20 years, and 10.9 percent have been employed for 20 years or more. Concerning the educational qualifications of the respondents, the Table indicates that 27.1 percent of them hold an SSCE; 48.6 percent possess a Diploma, and 18.8 percent have a first degree

Instruments

The study examined factors like Perceived Job Support and Job Satisfaction as independent variables, while Workers Productivity was considered the dependent variable. A five-point item scale was employed to assess the variables, with scale values ranging from 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. The materials were modified based on earlier research. The researcher performs multivariate analysis with Smart-PLS version 2 to evaluate the model and to test the hypotheses of the study. The PLS-SEM modeling approach allows the researcher to evaluate the complete measurement model and explore relationships with their corresponding measurements (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson, 2010). Therefore, this study employed PLS-SEM algorithms to assess the measurement and structural models

Validity and Reliability of Measures

As previously stated, the paper utilized PLS-SEM algorithms to evaluate the reliability and validity of constructs through the analysis of the measurement model. The evaluation of reliability and validity of constructs serves as the criteria in PLS-SEM analysis for determining the adequacy of the model fit (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013). The researcher thus performed a reliability analysis to assess the internal consistency of the measure. The specific outcomes of the validity and reliability analysis, based on Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted, are presented in Table 2. The table indicates that the composite reliability for the constructs within the model exceeds the benchmark of 0.70, with values ranging from 0.853 to 0.913 respectively (Hair et al., 2014). Additionally, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ranges from 0.541 to 0.538, indicating that the minimum standard of 0.50 is met (Hair, et al., 2013). The importance of the path coefficient (R2) was also shown in the Table. It indicates that the variables accounted for 89.1 percent of the variance in direct relationships. Therefore, it was thought that all the constructs possessed sufficient reliability

Table 2: Showing the AVE, CR and R²

Constructs	CR	AVE	R2
Perceive Job Support (PJS)	0.853	0.547	0.891
Job Satisfaction (JS)	0.913	0.638	
Workers Productivity (WP)	0.853	0.541	

Table 3: Latent Variable Correlations and Square Roots of AVE

Constructs	1	2	3
PJS	0.936		
JS	0.736	0.749	
WP	0.761	0.772	0.925

The present research utilized one of the most widely used methods for determining discriminant validity, known as the Fornell and Larcker criterion. This approach is accomplished by contrasting the squared correlations between the constructs with the AVE of each individual construct (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Table 3 presents the outcomes of the discriminant validity test using the Fornell and Larcker criterion carried out in this study. The results indicate that the squared correlations for all variables in this study were lower than the AVE as measured by the indicators of the variables. This indicates that both discriminant and convergent validity meet the required standards

Hypothesis Testing

In evaluating the hypothesis, the present research employed the PLS-SEM bootstrapping technique to assess the significance of the path coefficients. The study proposed that H1. A positive correlation exists between Perceived Job Support and Employee Productivity; H2 indicates a positive correlation between Job Satisfaction and Employee Productivity

Table 4: Summary of Findings and Hypothesis Testing

Hypotheses	Construct	Beta	Standard Error	T Statistics	P-value	Decision
H1	PJS -> WP	-0.06	0.03	1.95	0.00	Supported
H2	JS-> WP	1.03	0.02	35.05	0.00	Supported

DISCUSSION

The study explored the connection between Perceived Job Support, Job Satisfaction, and Worker Productivity among the Non-Academic Staff of UAS Polytechnic Sokoto, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The demographic information of the respondents was analyzed utilizing SPSS software version 23. The PLS-SEM analysis indicated statistical evidence of a positive relationship between the latent variables (PJS and WP), (JS and WP). The results of the research aligned closely with earlier studies concerning the connection between the target variables (Baba, & Ghazali, 2017; Bakhshi & Rani, 2009; Cagliyan, Attar & Derra, 2017; Durrani, Li & Yalalova, 2017; Rezaeizadeh, Monfared, & Ghasemipour, 2015; Yazicioglu & Topaloglu, 2009). This suggests that perceived job support and job satisfaction could positively influence the productivity of employees, especially the non-academic staff at UAS Polytechnic Sokoto. This is because employees who feel supported by the organization and are satisfied with their work will easily concentrate on their tasks. This aligns with the argument made by Manouchehri, Branch, and Katoul (2014), who observed that when employees perceive fairness in their treatment, they are likely to demonstrate positive behaviors that foster strong commitment to their work and reduce turnover intentions, ultimately resulting in increased productivity within the organizations (Manouchehri, Branch & Katoul, 2014).

CONCLUSION

The research examined the impact of perceived job support and job satisfaction on employee productivity at UAS Polytechnic in Sokoto State, Nigeria. From the 377 questionnaires sent out, only 228 valid responses were collected from the participants. The collected data was examined using Smart PLS-SEM version 2, and empirical findings show solid support for the two hypothesis statements. Building upon previous research, the present study confirmed all hypotheses, indicating that these findings have significant implications for administrators, managers, and policymakers in organizations, emphasizing the need for strict adherence to justice and fairness in almost all organizational processes. Examples include hiring, advancement, relocation, pay, discipline, etc. Furthermore, the study revealed that employees are generally willing to stay and strive for the organization's goals and objectives if they feel supported by the organization and are content with their positions. Drawing from the findings above, the paper advises incorporating an intervening variable like a moderator or mediator into the model. A comparable study should be carried out in other regions of the country to generate findings. Additional studies may also explore private sector organizations

REFERENCES

- Abdulsalam, D. & Mohammed, A. (2012). Motivation and Job Performance of Academic Staff of State Universities in Nigeria: The Case of Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(14), 142–148. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v7n14p142>
- Ahmad, N. (2014). Impact of Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance on the Employee Satisfaction. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 1(1), 84–92.
- Ali, W. U., Raheem, A. R., Nawaz, A., & Imamuddin, K. (2014). Impact of Stress on Job Performance: An Empirical study of the Employees of Private Sector Universities of Karachi, Pakistan. *Research Journal of Management Sciences*, 3(7), 14–17.
- Allen, J.N. & Meyer, J. . (1991). A Three-Component Model Conceptualization of Organizational Commitment. *Human Resource Management Review* ., 1(1), 62–89.
- Allen DG, Shore LM, Griffeth RW(2003), The role of perceived organizational support and supportive human resource practices in the turnover process. *J Manag.* 29 (1): 99-118.
- Altindis, S. (2011). Job motivation and organizational commitment among the health professionals : A

- questionnaire survey. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(21), 8601–8609.
- Baba, A. I., & Ghazali, S. B. (2017). Procedural, Interactional and Distributive Justice to Amplify Commitment of Public Sector Employees in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5(8), 55–64.
- Celik, M., & Sarituk, M. (2012). Organizational justice and motivation relationship; The case of adiyaman University. *Istanbul Ticoret Universiti Sosya Bilimler Degisi*, 11(21), 353–382.
- Chen, S., Wu, W., Chang, C., Lin, C., Kung, J., Weng, H., Lin, Y., & Lee, S. (2015). Organizational justice, trust, and identification and their effects on organizational commitment in hospital nursing staff. *BMC Health Services Research*, 15, 1–17.
- Dodman, K. & Zadeh, M. R. N. (2014). Examining the relationship between perceived organizational justice and dimensions of organizational commitment. *International Journal of Advanced Biological and Biomedical Research*, 2(7), 2319–2326.
- Edwards, B. D., Bell, S. T., Arthur, W., & Decuir, A. D. (2008). Relationships between facets of job satisfaction and task and contextual performance. *Applied Psychology*, 57(3), 441–465. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1464-0597.2008.00328.x>
- Eisenberger R, Huntington R, Hutchison S, Sowa D: Perceived organizational support. *J (1986) Appl Psychol.* 71 (3): 500-507.
- Eisenberger R, Armeli S, Rexwinkel B, Lynch PD, Rhoades L(2001), Reciprocation of perceived organizational support. *J Appl Psychol.* 86 (1): 42.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50.
- Hui C, Wong A, Tjosvold D(2007), Turnover intention and performance in China: the role of positive affectivity, chinese values, perceived organizational support and constructive controversy. *J Occup Organ Psychol.* 80 (4): 735-751. 10.1348/096317906X171037.
- Ismail, A., Hasan, A. B. M., & Sulaiman, A. Z. (2010). Supervisor's role as an antecedent of training transfer and motivation to learn in training programs. *Economica*, 7(2), 18-37.
- Judge TA, Thoresen CJ, Bono JE, Patton GK(2001) The job satisfaction–job performance relationship: a qualitative and quantitative review. *Psychol Bull.* 127 (3): 376.
- Khurram S (2009), Perceived organizational support, antecedents and consequences. *South Asian J Manag.* 7.
- Putter, S. E. (2013). Making training stick : a close examination of how trainee readiness, supervisor support, and practice foster transfer in a mobile technology based training program. PhDDissertation. Retrieved from: https://dspace.library.colostate.edu/bitstream/handle/10217/80969/Putter_colostate_0053A_12035.pdf?sequence
- Miao RT (2011), Perceived organizational support, Job satisfaction, task performance and organizational citizenship behavior in china. *J Behav Appl Manag.* 12 (2): 105-127.
- Rhoades, L., & Eisenberger, R. (2002). Perceived organizational support: a review of the literature: American Psychological Association. 84(4), 698-714.
- Rickett M:(2002), Attitudinal organizational commitment and job performance: a meta–analysis. *J Organ Behav.* 23 (3): 257-266. 10.1002/job.141.
- Rosen CC, Levy PE, Hall RJ(2006), Placing perceptions of politics in the context of the feedback environment, employee attitudes, and job performance. *J Appl Psychol.* 91 (1): 211.
- Stamper CL, Johlke MC (2003), The impact of perceived organizational support on the relationship between boundary spanner role stress and work outcomes. *J Manag.* 29 (4): 569-588.
- Takeuchi R, Wang M, Marinova SV, Yao X(2009), Role of domain-specific facets of perceived organizational support during expatriation and implications for performance. *Organ Sci.* 20 (3): 621-634. 10.1287/orsc.1080.0403.
- Van der Klink, J., Blonk, R., Schene, A. H., & Van Dijk, F. (2001). The benefits of interventions for work-related stress. *American journal of public health*, 91(2), 270-281
- Witt LA, Wilson JW(1991), Moderating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between equity and extra-role behaviors. *J Soc Psychol.* 131 (2): 247-252. 10.1080/00224545.1991.9713847.